

Report on open idea challenge and co-creation workshops

Deliverable 3.2

Version 1.0

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List of abbreviations

ATM	Automated teller machine
BCT	Behavioural change technique
B2C	Business-to-consumer
CEO	Chief executive officer
D	Deliverable
DUT	Driving Urban Transitions
M	Month
SME	Small and medium enterprises
T	Task
UX	User experience
V	Version
WP	Work Package

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Administrative information

Basic information on the SuCoLo project and this deliverable:

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Project coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (SRFG), Salzburg, Austria; project coordinator: Michael Thelen
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Purpose of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on the activities carried out as part of T3.2 “Open idea challenges, co-creation workshops with living-lab methods” within the SuCoLo project (WP3). This task started in M4 and ended in M15 and included the organisation and conduction of an open idea challenge, as well as the facilitation of co-creation workshops.

Additionally, the activities outlined in this document also indirectly contribute to T4.1 “Design and prepare accessible and inclusive pilots with local stakeholders”, which took place from M10 to M15. These activities involved collaborative co-creation and design processes with citizens, companies' representative and authorities.

Moreover, the activities are partially supported by T5.3 “Events, presentations and publications” (WP5).

The deliverable provides a comprehensive overview that will be beneficial for all subsequent project tasks; particularly those in WP4, which focuses on the three SuCoLo research pilots.

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a report on the activities under T3.2 “Open idea challenges, co-creation workshops and living-lab methods” within the SuCoLo project (WP3) and T4.1 “Design and prepare accessible and inclusive pilots with local stakeholders” (WP4). Moreover, they are supported by T5.3 “Events, presentations and publications” (WP5). These activities involved an international open idea challenge for motivation for green logistic choices and a local open idea challenge in Merano. The deliverable also provides an overview of co-creation workshops for sustainable logistic solutions held in the piloting locations: Salzburg, Leipzig and Merano.

The open idea challenge, titled “Wanted: Sustainable last mile delivery heroes,” aimed to engage citizens across Austria, Germany, Italy and Sweden in contributing feedback and innovative ideas for modalities of sustainable last-mile logistics. Running from September 2024 to January 2025, the campaign received a total of 53 applications.

Additionally, from December 2024 to February 2025, the ideation campaign “My Merano, My Cargo Bike” was organised to involve the citizens in Merano in the local SuCoLo pilot. This campaign featured a naming competition for five cargo bikes and the scooter designed for people with disabilities from local bike-sharing program. The public were invited to vote for their favorite names and submit additional proposals, resulting in 48 name ideas.

Both campaigns were hosted on SFRG’s IdeaSpace platform, which has an active community of over 2,000 members. Each featured a professional jury, with the international completion additionally incorporating community voting.

A series of co-creation workshops, began at Salzburg Science City, Itzling, on 26 September 2024. The event was organised by SFRG and brought together a diverse mix of participants. The primary objective was to evaluate a webshop prototype designed to integrate behaviour change techniques for promoting sustainable delivery behaviours. The session gathered age-specific feedback on different aspects such as willingness to pay for cargo bike delivery, preference for motivational techniques, visualization of information on webshop, etc.

The next workshop, titled “Workshop on mobility and shopping behaviour in Lützschena-Stahmeln” was held on 15 January 2025 in Leipzig. It was organised by ULEI and the associated project partner, the City of Leipzig’s Office of Economic Development. The session brought together residents of the Lützschena-Stahmeln district, representatives of the City of Leipzig and employees from a local bike courier service. The objective of the workshop was to gain insights into the needs of residents in this urban outskirts area and to develop a sustainable and inclusive delivery concept with local stakeholders.

One more co-creation workshop was conducted on 18 December 2024 in Merano. It was organised by STA in collaboration with Independent L, the Municipality of Merano and the HDS Traders’ Association. The event served as a crucial opportunity to analyse operational strategies and identify specific requirements for the successful implementation of two pilot services in sustainable mobility. The workshop was attended by institutional representatives, industry experts and local economic stakeholders.

The outcomes of the idea challenges and co-creation workshops are being considered by the SoCoLo project partners in their planning of the next steps, particularly the research pilots.

1 Introduction and task description

The deliverable is based on activities and insights from the international open idea challenge aimed at generating new ideas to motivate consumers to choose green logistics options, as well as the open ideation campaign in Merano, which involved citizens in the beginning of the piloting phase in Italy. In addition, the deliverable describes co-creation workshops, including those held to support the design the pilots.

This work was realised within WP3 “Sustainable logistics choices and co-creation” with a focus on T3.2 “Open idea challenges, co-creation workshops with living-lab methods.” As part of this task, an open idea challenge for “Motivation for green logistic choices” was organised in the four partner countries – Austria, Germany, Italy and Sweden. In addition, co-creation workshops focusing on sustainable logistic solutions with local stakeholders were organised in Leipzig and Salzburg. Another workshop, using living lab methods to integrate cargo-bikes into suburban logistics solutions was held in Merano. All workshops were designed to involve citizens, city representatives, and logistics providers. The lead partners for this task were SRFG, SIC and STA (specifically for cargo-bicycles in Merano), with strong support by all project partners.

This deliverable is also associated with activities carried out under T4.1 “Design and prepare accessible and inclusive pilots with local stakeholders”, within WP4 “SuCoLo Research Pilots”. This included co-creating and designing the SuCoLo research pilots for sustainable goods logistics in collaboration with local stakeholders (citizens, companies, authorities, etc.). The pilots focus on bicycle-based delivery and inclusive pick-up stations that enrich neighbourhoods, as well as digital behaviour change interventions to motivate usage. One of the key activities under this task was the open ideation competition “My Merano, My Cargo Bike”, which took place in Italy. Moreover, local co-creation workshops in Salzburg, Leipzig and Merano, part of T3.2, also indirectly contributed valuable input for the preparation of the research pilots (T4.1). The lead partners for each pilot location and their respective workshops are: Merano – STA, with support of HDS (local businesses) and IND (regarding barrier-free accessibility for all); in Leipzig – ULEI, with support by LEIP; Salzburg – SRFG, with support of VIA, SVV and IND (for accessible solutions).

The report was prepared by all SuCoLo partners, with Sustainability InnoCenter coordinating the process.

2. Open ideation campaign “Sustainable Last-mile Delivery Heroes” (all partner countries)

The Open Innovation Idea Challenge aimed at the broad involvement of citizens (i.e., “the crowd”) throughout all four consortium partner countries to feedback, solutions and ideas for four modalities of sustainable last-mile logistics that the SuCoLo project is engaged in. Partner SRFG, which has hosted the idea platform “*IdeaSpace*” (<https://www.ideaspace.cc/en/>) since 2019, brought its extensive experience in conducting idea campaigns across various sectors to the initiative, with an active community of 2,000+ active members.

Figure 1 Landing page of the IdeaSpace website

2.1. Preparation period

To ensure the idea campaigns effectively supported the SuCoLo project’s objectives and met the requirements of the partners, all consortium members were involved in the setup process from the outset.

During the 2nd SuCoLo consortium meeting on 11 March 2024, the concept of crowdsourcing and the functionality of the *IdeaSpace* platform was introduced to consortium partners. A short workshop was conducted to gather feedback on the campaign’s key elements, including the questions posed, target groups, expectations for the depth and quality of submitted ideas, and the voting process. This feedback was incorporated into the campaign’s planning and subsequently validated during monthly consortium meetings.

Figure 2 Discussing SuCoLo's crowdsourcing strategy at the 2nd SuCoLo consortium meeting, 11 March 2024

Additionally, consortium partners were also tasked with nominating local jury experts in their locality and promoting the campaign within their respective networks to ensure widespread participation and a diverse range of ideas.

2.2. Application phase

The campaign was ultimately titled “**Wanted: Sustainable last mile delivery heroes**” and sought for innovative ideas for sustainable solutions that raise awareness of green alternatives, support local initiatives, promote sustainable collection and delivery methods and motivate consumers to make environmentally conscious choices.

To ensure broad accessibility in all consortium partner countries, the campaign was promoted in three languages: **English, German and Italian.**

APPLICATION PHASE	COMMUNITY & JURY VOTING	WINNERS ANNOUNCEMENT	AWARD CEREMONY ONLINE
Sept 15 - Nov 27	Nov 28 - Dec 16	Dec	Jan 21

Figure 3 Timeline of the IdeaSpace campaign “Wanted: Sustainable last mile delivery heroes”

Call text

Are you ready to champion sustainability? Living in the outskirts or rural areas shouldn't mean compromising on eco-friendly choices, especially in the crucial final stretch of goods logistics.

For this idea competition in the framework of the SuCoLo research project, we are looking for innovative ideas for sustainable solutions that raise awareness of green alternatives, support local initiatives, promote sustainable collection and delivery methods and motivate consumers to make environmentally conscious choices.

Join this movement – bring your ideas, whether solo or as a team, and help shape the future of logistics to be sustainable, smart, and livable! You can submit your ideas in the following areas (maximum three per category per person):

 Category “Behaviour Change”: How can we encourage behaviour change and awareness among consumers in rural and suburban areas to adopt more sustainable practices when ordering and receiving goods? What (digital) features and strategies could effectively support these behaviour changes?

 Category “Green Online Store”: How should a “green” online store be designed to attract environmentally conscious consumers and encourage sustainable delivery? What key features are crucial (e.g., information on delivery emissions, promotion of local supply chains, choice of delivery vehicles), and how should they be implemented?

 Category “Perfect Pick-up Station”: Imagine the perfect pick-up station. What amenities and incentives would encourage people to choose pick-up delivery for their goods?

 Category “Ultimate Booking Platform”: Design the ultimate booking platform for cargo bike sharing that can facilitate citizens to move/deliver goods in a smooth and sustainable way. What features would be essential (e.g., user-friendly booking system, route optimization, real-time data integration and pricing), and how can these be implemented?

Application form

The applicants were required to address the following questions as part of their submission:

- Title
- Description
- What concrete benefits does your idea bring to the selected topic area (1-3 sentences):
- In your opinion, are there any potential challenges (e.g. technical, legal, financial) that need to be solved?
- Do you know of any successful similar concepts/projects? If so, please list them here
- Who do you think could implement this idea? (Yourself, a specific company, several companies, municipality, state, tourism association, ...)

Prizes

In order to incentivise participation from “the crowd”, the following prizes awaited the winners:

Prize 1: Voucher worth 250,- Euro for <https://www.avocadostore.de/> or <https://fairschenkt.at/>

Prize 2: Voucher worth 150,- Euro for <https://www.avocadostore.de/> or <https://fairschenkt.at/>

Prize 3: Voucher worth 100,- Euro for <https://www.avocadostore.de/> or <https://fairschenkt.at/>

Additionally, the Community Winner Idea (i.e., the winner chosen by the IdeaSpace community members) earned a CHIBA Sportswear rain poncho and CHIBA Sportswear rain trousers sponsored by partner STA.

Jury composition

The jury comprised the following nine experts, representing diverse fields and expertise in sustainable last-mile logistics, to harness their expertise and rate the ideas:

- **Henrike Bauer**, Business Development & International Affairs, Hafen Wien (Austria)
- **Manuela Budich**, Office for Economic Development, City of Leipzig (Germany)
- **Michael M. Damisch**, CEO, DieBoten.at (Austria)
- **Svante Hagström**, Collaboration and Innovation Manager, Sustainability InnoCenter (Sweden)
- **Prof. Dr. André Ludwig**, Professor, University of Leipzig (Germany)
- **Valentina Mena**, Project manager cycling mobility, Green Mobility, STA – Südtiroler Transportinfrastrukturen AG (Italy)
- **Carmen Monica**, Architect, Office for Infrastructure and Sustainable Mobility, Autonomous Province of Bolzano – Südtirol (Italy)
- **Prof. Dr. Dorothea Schaffner**, Professor, University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland (Switzerland)
- **Martin Stampfer**, Head of the Competence Center for Urban Development, NOI Techpark Südtirol (Italy)

Jury process

The jury process consisted of two components: community voting and expert voting.

Table 1 Jury process and evaluation process of the open ideation campaign “Sustainable Last-mile Delivery Heroes”

Voting type	Description
Community Voting	From 28 November to 8 December 2024, all members of the IdeaSpace platform were invited to vote for their favorite projects. The project with the highest number of votes from the community was automatically included in the next stage of evaluation.
Expert Voting	<p>The expert jury evaluation was conducted in two online rounds, followed by a final meeting:</p> <p>In the first round (28.11.24 - 08.12.24), jury members were assigned around 15 of the ideas submitted, which had to be evaluated according to the jury criteria. The best 9 ideas from the overall ranking moved on, supplemented by the winning idea from the community voting.</p> <p>In the second round (10.12.24 - 16.12.24), jury members had to evaluate the shortlisted projects using the same criteria.</p> <p>The Final Jury Meeting was held online on 17 December 2024. In this meeting, the top three winners were determined from the best shortlisted projects in a moderated process.</p>

Jury Criteria and Evaluation

The evaluation criteria were developed and weighed as follows:

Table 2 Jury criteria of the campaign “Sustainable Last-mile Delivery Heroes”

Criteria	Weight
Originality: How innovative and creative is the solution in the specific context? Does it differ from existing concepts, and does it add value?	10 %
Ecological and social impact: What positive effects does the idea have on the environment, quality of life and communities?	20 %
Feasibility: How realistic and practical is the implementation considering resources, feasibility and chances of success?	25 %
Scalability: Is the idea flexible and adaptable to be effective in other regions or on a larger scale?	25 %
Local embeddedness: How well is the idea adapted to local conditions and needs and promotes sustainable development?	20 %

Promotion

The idea campaign was promoted via the IdeaSpace and SuCoLo communication channels, as well as the networks of the consortium partners. In total, **70 social media posts** were created by Salzburg Research out of which **42 posts** were on the channels of IdeaSpace, reaching approximately **3,061** people on LinkedIn. All mentioned social media material was further shared by the SuCoLo LinkedIn channel. Moreover, 6 newsletters were sent out on the <https://my.ideaspace.cc/login> platform, directly to the members of IdeaSpace regarding the SuCoLo idea competition.

Figure 4 Example of the IdeaSpace campaign's LinkedIn outreach

Additionally, the campaign was integrated into courses at the following universities and universities of applied sciences, where the students' task was to submit ideas for the campaign:

- University of Applied Sciences Salzburg: English-language bachelor's program "Sustainability in Tourism"
- University of Applied Sciences Salzburg: German-language bachelor's program "Sustainability in Tourism"
- University of Applied Sciences Salzburg: German-language bachelor's program "Business Informatics and Digital Transformation"

- FHNW University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland bachelor's program "Business Psychology"
- University of Leipzig: Master's program "Business Information Systems"

The campaign was also promoted through a workshop held at the STA headquarters in Bolzano on 17 October 2024. Participants from the "Radtisch" action group, which includes individuals actively involved in the field of cycling mobility in South Tyrol at both administrative and tourism levels, were invited. The workshop was attended by 8 participants and one moderator. During the session, 3 proposals were presented, which were subsequently entered on the Open Idea Platform.

Figure 5 IdeaSpace Radtisch workshop in Bolzano

Promotional Materials

Many promotional materials ("sujets") were developed and utilized for the campaign, e.g., flyers, certificates, visuals for social media, posters, with some examples below:

Figure 6 IdeaSpace campaign promotional visuals

Submitted Ideas

A total of **53 ideas** were submitted, distributed across the following categories, with the category “Ultimate Booking Platform” receiving the most submissions:

- **Category “Behaviour Change”**: 12 submissions
- **Category “Green Online Store”**: 6 submissions
- **Category “Perfect Pick-up Station”**: 16 submissions
- **Category “Ultimate Booking Platform”**: 19 submissions

All submitted ideas can be accessed on IdeaSpace here:

<https://my.ideaspace.cc/kvp/33d7233b-0dd9-4cba-b83a-1ab56a2f3c06>

Final event and best awarded ideas, next steps

The following top 3 ideas and the community winner idea were awarded:

1st Place: [Idea 46 – „PaketPlus: The human pick-up station“](#) (category “Perfect Pick-up Station”)

An idea that not only improves the efficiency of the last mile but also creates social and ecological value. The concept combines practical everyday usability with innovation and a clear focus on community and sustainability. With the most community likes, the idea was also chosen as the Community Winner.

2nd Place: [Idea 38 – „GreenHub 360“](#) (category “Perfect Pick-up Station”)

The GreenHub 360 idea for the perfect pick-up station solves an important delivery issue by using storage for both the collection and drop-off of items at a strategically located point. Collecting all deliveries for a household or community at one point and picking them up in one go reduces costly last-mile transport.

🏆 **3rd Place:** [Idea 11 – “Community monopoly for the last mile: Sustainable and local logistics through community-based delivery organizations”](#) (category “Behaviour Change”)

This idea is an innovative and holistic approach to sustainable logistics that aligns with ecological, economic and social benefits. By enabling communities to organize and optimize last-mile deliveries, traffic congestion and emissions are reduced, the local economy is strengthened and the quality of life for citizens is improved.

🏆 **The community winner:** [Idea 46 – „PaketPlus: The human pick-up station“](#) (category “Perfect Pick-up Station”)

The **Award Ceremony** took place on **Tuesday, 20 January 2025**, from **4:00 to 4:45 PM** via Zoom. The event was combined with a **Business Speed Networking Session**, providing an opportunity for the winners, jurors, the IdeaSpace community, and consortium partners to connect and network. A total of **18 participants** attended the session.

Figure 7 IdeaSpace award ceremony, 21 January 2025

As a next step in the project, the project consortium will have access to the ideas and will incorporate them when applicable in further project tasks, specifically what concerns the design and preparation of the SuCoLo research pilots (e.g., T3.3 Inventory of behaviour change strategies for sustainable consumer logistics choices, T3.4 Behaviour change guidebook and digital behavioural interventions tool, and T4.1 Design and prepare accessible and inclusive pilots with local stakeholders).

3. Open ideation campaign “My Merano, My Cargo Bike” (Italy)

In the framework of the piloting of the SuCoLo project in Merano, Merano’s bike-sharing is expanding: five cargo bikes and an electric scooter specifically designed for people with disabilities will be made available to citizens. To involve the citizens in this project in a playful way, a name competition was conducted to find the perfect names for each cargo bike and the scooter. The campaign was titled “**My Merano, My Cargobike.**” It was conducted and promoted in **German and Italian**. In the beginning, communication experts developed and suggested some name ideas. The crowd was asked to vote for their favourites and submit up to two additional proposals on the IdeaSpace platform.

Figure 8 Promotion for “My Merano, My Cargobike”

Concerning the timing of the ideation campaign, it commenced on 20 December 2024, with the final award ceremony taking place on 6 February 2025.

Figure 9 Timeline of the IdeaSpace campaign “My Merano, My Cargobike”

Application form

The applicants were required to suggest a title and give a little bit of background information about the name that they chose to name the cargo bike.

Prizes

Six of the best ideas submitted by the community won a **CHIBA Sportswear rain poncho**. Additionally, **the most active user** who interacted the most on the platform (comments, proposals, likes) was awarded with a package of bicycle gadgets.

Jury composition

The jury comprised the following three experts, representing diverse fields and expertise in sustainable last-mile logistics, to harness their expertise and rate the ideas:

- **Alice Banfi**, Communication, STA – South Tyrolean Transport Infrastructure AG
- **David Felz**, Coordinator of Bicycle Mobility, STA – South Tyrolean Transport Infrastructure AG
- **Martin Stampfer**, Head of Competence Center for Local Development, NOI Techpark Südtirol

Jury Criteria and Evaluation

The evaluation criteria were developed and weighed as follows:

Table 3 Jury criteria of the open ideation campaign “My Merano, My Cargobike”

Criteria	Weight
Originality: How creative is the proposed name? Is the story behind the choice original and does it fit the context?	70 %
Bilingualism: Does the proposed name work in both German and Italian, or does it only come across in one language (Italian, German, English)?	30 %

Promotional Materials

Many promotional materials (“sujets”) were developed and utilized for the campaign, e.g., flyers, certificates, visuals for social media, posters, with some examples below:

Figure 10 LinkedIn outreach for the idea campaign "My Merano, My Cargobike"

Submitted Ideas

A total of **48 name ideas** were submitted. All submitted ideas can be accessed on IdeaSpace here: <https://my.ideaspace.cc/kvp/f2e207a5-6f69-4073-83a9-e3cebb1e18ba>.

Final event and best awarded ideas, next steps

The following top 6 name ideas were awarded, which will be implemented as the names of the 6 newly procured cargo bikes in Merano as part of the SuCoLo project:

- 🏆 [CaptainCargo](#)
- 🏆 [CargoLina](#)
- 🏆 [C. Argonaut](#)
- 🏆 [EcoMover](#)
- 🏆 [Pass\(r\)gino](#)
- 🏆 [Sissi-Cruiser](#)

The **Award Ceremony** took place on **Thursday, 6 February 2025**, at **4:30 PM** via Zoom and included the IdeaSpace jury members and all the winners. The total of **8 participants** attended the session, where the idea winners had the chance to voice the story behind their names.

Figure 11 "My Merano, My Cargobike" award ceremony, 6 February 2025

4. Co-creation workshops for sustainable logistic solutions with local stakeholders

4.1. Salzburg co-creation workshop

Overview

On 26 September 2024, Salzburg Research hosted such a co-creation workshop at Salzburg Science City, Itzling, as part of the project. The session brought together a diverse mix of 13 participants, including 4 Gen Z representatives, 6 millennials, and 4 participants from an older age group, out of which 3 were pensioners. The aim was to collaboratively assess sustainable last-mile delivery solutions using cargo bikes. The central focus was to evaluate a webshop prototype designed to integrate behaviour change techniques (BCTs) for promoting sustainable delivery behaviours. Moreover, participants split into working groups based on their age, and the task was to decide their willingness to pay for cargo bike delivery as well as their preference for motivational techniques.

Figure 12 Invitation and participants at the co-creation workshop, 26 September 2024, Salzburg

To guide discussions, each participant was assigned to one of three tailored personas: “Jonas” (a young student without a car – “Generation Z”), “Helena” (a middle-aged professional – “millennial”) and “Silvia” (a retired pensioner – “boomer”).

The purpose of using personas was:

- ✓ To bring focus and structure to the discussion, guiding participants to think beyond personal biases and consider the needs of the larger population
- ✓ To encourage participants to empathize with user groups they may not belong to. This ensures that the solutions developed are inclusive and consider a broader spectrum of society
- ✓ To provide clarity, further aiding the design of targeted, practical solutions

These personas helped explore diverse user perspectives on sustainable delivery options and identify their varying priorities.

Table 4 Three employed user personas

Jonas	Helena	Silvia
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 65 years old • Cohabiting • Pensioner • Two grown-up children • Worked as an event manager; still helps out sometimes • Lives in house; parking lot in front of door • Dog 		

The workshop directed the following questions to the respondents:

“When you are online shopping...

1. *What are your needs and requirements to choose cargo bike delivery?”*
2. *What is your willingness to pay and time expectations for cargo bike delivery?”*
3. *Which motivation/behaviour change techniques would you prefer on an online shop?”*
4. *What is your level of comfort of our behaviour change techniques?”*
5. *What would you change about the UX and layout of our webshop prototype?”*

Furthermore, there were four group exercises which the participants engaged in:

Figure 13 The four employed exercises

Figure 14 Working groups at the co-creation workshop

Results

Participants provided detailed feedback on the webshop prototype, focusing on improving usability and aligning with user expectations. Key suggestions included enhancing text and image contrast for better readability, updating the homepage image to display realistic cargo bike-compatible products, fixing the shopping cart to show shipping costs only after a delivery method is selected, and potentially adding a “deal timer” to encourage urgency. Recommendations also highlighted increasing the size of key interface elements, such as the shopping cart and text.

While certain ideas, like GIFs of cargo bikes or repeat customer features, were deemed out of scope for this prototype, the feedback offers a clear roadmap for future improvements. The persona exercise further identified strong preferences for specific BCTs, including environmental impact messaging to highlight CO₂ reductions, a default sustainable delivery option, and goal-setting prompts encouraging commitment to eco-friendly choices.

Results question “How many euros would you spend on sustainable cargo bike delivery?”

- ✓ A majority of participants are willing to pay 1 euro or more for the sustainable delivery option. Although many participants resonated with the fact that the amount of euros they are willing to pay is also dependent on how high the shopping cart is.

Results question “How does your purchase satisfaction change depending on the price for the sustainable cargo bike delivery?”

- ✓ For all participants except for one, most would be moderately or highly satisfied to pay at least something for the sustainable option. Notably, the persona “Helena” was prepared to pay the most out of all personas for sustainable delivery, with the other two personas scattered (green sticker = persona “Jonas”, red sticker = persona “Helena”, yellow sticker = persona “Silvia”).

Figure 15 Consumer price elasticity for sustainable cargo bike delivery

Results question “How does your purchase satisfaction change with different delivery times for the sustainable cargo bike delivery service?”

- ✓ Generally, most shoppers would accept a delivery time of 1-5 days, with the most respondents being highly satisfied with a delivery time of 1-2 days. Generally, there was a negative correlation concerning the delivery time and satisfaction rate. Notably, persona “Silvia” was willing to wait the longest for her package.

Figure 16 Consumer time elasticity for sustainable cargo bike delivery

Results question “How appealing do you find these motivational BCTs? Select 3 BCTs individually that your persona would prefer and justify your choice. What would motivate you? Do you have your own suggestions for BCTs?” (Task: participants were given 10 different BCT visualisations on a sheet of paper).

- ✓ Across all personas, a top BCT type was *Information about the environmental impact*, either taking form with the text “help reduce CO2 emissions by choosing cargo bike delivery” or by employing an information box.
- ✓ Among the persona “Silvia”, the notable first choice which deviated compared to the other two personas, was the BCT *Default option*.
- ✓ In third place for two personas (“Jonas” and “Helena”), *Information about social consequences* was chosen

Table 5 Top three choices by each persona (individual and grouped)

Persona	1 st choice	2 nd choice	3 rd choice
Silvia	#8 Default option is the sustainable choice	#4 Information about environmental impact (help reduce CO2 emissions by choosing cargo bike delivery)	#1 Objective (pop-up on the shop`s homepage that allows customers to set the goal of choosing sustainable delivery methods
Jonas	#4 Information about environmental impact (help reduce CO2 emissions by choosing cargo bike delivery)	#6 Information about environmental impact (information box about the more sustainable choice)	#10 Information about social consequences
Helena	#4 Information about environmental impact (help reduce CO2 emissions by choosing cargo bike delivery)	#6 Information about environmental impact (information box about the more sustainable choice)	#10 Information about social consequences

Figure 17 Ten example BCTs given to the participants for rating and discussion and ranking during the workshop

Results question “Do you have any ideas for visualizing info text/BCTs in the test webshop, e.g. images, colors, sounds, videos, comics, bots, etc.?”

- ✓ The specific suggestions are below, along with the SuCoLo team’s response for future integration:

Table 6 Participant UX feedback and response

Participant UX feedback	Response (accept or reject and explanation)
Clearly mark which products can be delivered by cargo-bike - Possibly with pop-up asking for zip-code in the beginning	Reject Valuable for a real shop, but for the experiment not necessary, as only products will be included that can be delivered by cargo bike
Include GIF or graphic of cargo bike on the main page	Reject Would prime the participants and falsify the results, not applicable for our experiment except maybe as separate BCT
Describe collective effort how many kilometres or products have been delivered by cargo bike	Reject Difficult to replicate in our experiment as it is difficult for firms to ascertain that value
Sad smiley that pops up if unsustainable delivery option is chosen	Reject Won't be implemented, as it would be a different BCTs
Add positive "streak" for return customers	Reject Won't be implemented as we have no return customers for the experiment; the study is not longitudinal and does not track one's activity over time
Unspecific Feedback on CO2 (without numbers) CO2 savings in neutral tone	Reject Not possible due to EU Green Claims Directive
Ask for subjective effectivity of nudge and adjust presentation accordingly	Accept Asking for subjective effectivity will be considered for questionnaire (i.e., nudge acceptance scale) Adjusting presentation only feasible with repeated use of the workshop, so not for our experiment
Positive Reinforcement after finishing the shopping experience	Reject Won't implement in our experiment as it adds nothing of value. Might be interesting for a real shop with return customers
Do not include social media share buttons on bottom of the page	Reject Will still be included as it is custom on many webshops and does not influence the delivery choice
Higher Contrast for text and images	Accept Will be implemented
Fix shopping cart already shows sum including shipping cost before shipping is even selected	Accept Will be fixed
Add Login/Account option	Accept Will possibly be implemented as non-clickable feature

Increase size of text and shopping cart in the upper right corner	Accept Will be considered for future implementation
Change image on homepage to products that are more realistically used in the webshop and could be delivered via cargo bike	Accept Will be changed
Deal timer to promote urgency among the consumers	Accept Implementation will be discussed
Possibility for repeat purchases	Reject not feasible for our experiment, as we only have a one-time shopping experience planned that is not longitudinal

Figure 18 Respondent's UX feedback (post-it notes)

Lessons learned & next steps

The workshop provided important insights into participants' preferences and expectations regarding sustainable delivery options. By combining qualitative feedback with user-driven preferences for BCTs, the team accumulated a number of ideas to refine the webshop prototype further.

The feedback received helped the team to further optimize the user experience, align motivational techniques with user comfort levels, and support broader project goals of promoting behavioural shifts toward sustainable consumer choices, leading to several improvements for iteration 2.

Key updates include enhancing the text and image contrast for better readability, enlarging text and icons (e.g., the shopping cart) for improved visibility, and revising the shipping cost display so fees appear only after a delivery method is selected. Additionally, a non-clickable login/account option will be added for realism, and the homepage imagery will be updated to showcase more practical products suited for cargo bike delivery. Furthermore, a deal timer feature is under consideration to make the webshop more dynamic. These refinements aim to enhance usability, accessibility, and the overall realism of the webshop prototype that will be used in the Salzburg research pilot (T4.2).

4.2. Leipzig co-creation workshop

Overview

On 15 January 2025, the University of Leipzig and the associated project partner, the City of Leipzig's Office of Economic Development, hosted a co-creation workshop entitled "*Workshop on mobility and shopping behaviour in Lützschena-Stahmeln*" in the conference room of the Leipziger Hotel. The workshop participants ($N = 10$) were residents of Lützschena-Stahmeln (a locality in the north-west borough of Leipzig), representatives of the City of Leipzig and employees from a local bike courier. The objective of the workshop was to gain insights regarding the needs of residents of this urban outskirts area and to develop a sustainable and inclusive delivery concept together with local stakeholders. The focus here was on the creation of a concept for a pick-up station for goods that considers local and social conditions.

The workshop was announced with flyers and an advertisement in the December 2024 / January 2025 edition in the local newspaper *Auenkurier* (see figure 20, source: <http://www.luetzschena-stahmeln.de/auenkurier/2025/01.pdf>).

Figure 19 Co-creation workshop with local stakeholders

UNIVERSITÄT
LEIPZIG

Stadt Leipzig
Amt für Wirtschaftsförderung

**Workshopeinladung und Befragung zum
Mobilitäts- & Einkaufsverhalten in Lützschena-Stahmeln**

Die **Universität Leipzig** und das **Amt für Wirtschaftsförderung** der Stadt Leipzig untersuchen als lokale Vertreter im europäischen Forschungsprojekt SuCoLo das Mobilitäts- und Einkaufsverhalten der Leipziger Stadtrandgebiete. Mit Ihren Antworten suchen wir nach Alternativen für eine bessere Nahversorgung mit Waren aus der Innenstadt. Da wir mit unserer Forschung so nah wie möglich an der Basis sein wollen, bitten wir alle Einwohnerinnen und Einwohner von Lützschena-Stahmeln und den umliegenden Stadtteilen um Teilnahme an der anonymen **Kurzumfrage per QR-Code oder in Papierform**. Fragebögen in Papierform liegen u.a. in der Gärtnerei Thomas Gordelt, Elstergarten 9, 04159 Leipzig, aus. Geben Sie diese dort bitte wieder ab.

Möchten Sie sich aktiv in den Entwicklungs- und Veränderungsprozess einbringen? Dann melden Sie sich gerne zu unserem **Workshop am 15. Januar 2025, ab 16:00 Uhr im Hotel Leipzig**, Hallesche Str.190, 04159 Leipzig, an. Wir bitten um eine vorherige Registrierung, da die Teilnehmerzahl begrenzt ist. Bitte melden Sie sich bei Philipp Teitge unter philipp.teitge@leipzig.de oder Tel. 0341 / 123 5897

Haben Sie Fragen oder Anmerkungen, dann schreiben Sie uns! Informationen zum Projekt finden Sie unter <https://sucolo.eu/>

Figure 20 Survey and workshop advertisement in the Auenkurier

The workshop started with a brief introduction to the topic. The main aim was to gather important information at three walk-through stations (see figure 21 and 22). At the first station, the participants were asked about the current status of existing infrastructure, such as stores, bus stops, health care, etc., and what infrastructure they lack. The last thing they were allowed to do at this station was to make a wish for Lützschena-Stahmeln (L-S). The results are summarised in the table below.

Table 7 Available, missing and desired amenities in Lützschena-Stahmeln

What is available in L-S	What is not available in L-S	What should be available in L-S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • small grocery store • drugstore • post office (2x) • pharmacy • hardware store • garden center • gas station • ice cream shop • restaurants (2x) • hotel • physiotherapist (2x) • general doctor (2x) • hairdresser • car repair shop • vet • artists association • voluntary fire brigade 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sparkasse with an ATM machine • grocery store with a wide selection of goods • bakery • butcher • café • community centre • library • self-help repair shop • multipurpose room 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • stationary retail and local supply • public outdoor swimming pool • new construction of the primary school • a small bus to take older people to the next tram / S-Bahn stop (FLEXA) • park and ride at the S-Bahn station • park and ride at the tram station • multipurpose room for local associations • self-help repair shop • help with digital devices for older residents

At the second station, the participants were asked about their perfect delivery location for parcels. The results show that they would like a barrier-free, centrally located facility for meeting other residents next to a tram stop within walking distance. They suggest that the delivery location would be centrally located, near places such as the gas station, the hotel, an old brewery site that is currently derelict, the football club, the hairdresser or the garden centre. All suggested locations are located on or near the main street of Lützschena-Stahmeln.

Figure 21 Results of workshop participants' ideation

At station three, the participants had the task of creating their desired 15-minute neighbourhood along the flowers of proximity (Baquero & Lámiquiz, 2014), where a diagram of a flower is created together and each petal represents varying activities: education, health, commerce, housing, work and entertainment. Here, each of these categories has different amenities or services that must be located at different distances from home (5-, 15- or 30-minutes) depending on the preferences and needs of the residents.

Figure 22 Flower of proximity for Lützschena-Stahmeln

Table 8 Flower of proximity for Lützschena-Stahmeln

Distance	education	entertainment	housing	work	commerce	health
5-minutes	primary school kindergarten after school care	church pitches	parks multipurpose room for local associations playground locations for a walk			fitness center general doctor
15-minutes	Library High school	Meeting point for older people cinema			grocery store ATM Pharmacy Hairdresser Café restaurant	dentist hospital local sport group
30-minutes		Adult education centre courses opera theatre		Workplace	clothing shop hardware store	

Finally, the results were summarized orally and discussed freely with the participants.

Results

The ideal local supply concept for Lützschena-Stahmeln created by residents and local stakeholders would take into account the following gained insights:

- Residents have a lack of grocery stores with a variety of goods needed for daily life
- Participants desire rooms and areas where they can spend their free time together (e.g., a café, community center, library, outdoor pool, multifunctional room, etc.)
- To reach the city center by public transport, park and ride spaces must be created near public transport stops
- Older residents would like help with digital devices and repairing items

For the participants, important facilities – such as primary school, kindergartens, playgrounds, general practitioners, sports grounds, churches or natural areas – should be within 5 minutes

walking distance. For special doctors or services, people are prepared to walk 15 minutes. For culture and entertainment or work, residents are even willing to walk 30 minutes.

These results indicate that the residents of urban outskirts are particularly dependent on the delivery of everyday goods and that a possible pick-up station should take social aspects into account where the neighbours can meet. A pick-up station should either be centrally located or well connected to public transportation in Lützschena-Stahmeln. Due to the needs of older residents, an inclusive, possibly even non-digitalized solution for collecting the goods is recommended.

Lessons learned & next steps

The co-creation workshop with residents from Lützschena-Stahmeln provided important insights about their daily mobility and shopping behaviour. To emphasize, it is important to understand the special needs in contrast to city center residents.

Figure 23 Outskirt resident survey questionnaire

Going deeper as a next step, a survey was created to gather more detailed information about the habits of Lützschena-Stahmeln residents, which will end in the first week of March and be evaluated by the end of April 2025. Based on the results of the survey, the Leipzig research pilot's design (WP4) will take these findings into account. The anonymous survey is available in German via a QR-Code or as a paper questionnaire in three facilities in Lützschena-Stahmeln: a garden center, a physiotherapist studio and a hotel. Collection boxes are placed there. In addition, flyers were distributed, and posters were on display in the stores to increase awareness of the survey. The QR-code for the survey was also published in the local newspaper in the January and February 2025 editions. The QR-code will lead the reader to the survey tool of the University of Leipzig. The survey is about the mobility and shopping

behaviour of the outskirts residents, in particular of Lützschena-Stahmeln. The questions asked are about their means of transportation (e.g., by car, public transport, bike, etc.) to the city center of Leipzig, frequency of visiting the city centre, shopping motivation in the city center, types of purchases, local shopping needs, items that are ordered online, and preferences regarding receiving their delivery (including locations or desired delivery characteristics, e.g., speed, cost or sustainability). In order to categorize the survey's participants, the survey asks optional for demographic data. This survey aims to collect valuable insights that can help improve local logistics and shopping behaviour in Lützschena-Stahmeln and other comparable outskirts.

Figure 24 Poster and collection box for paper questionnaires

4.3. Merano co-creation workshop

Overview

On 18 December 2024, a co-creation workshop was held at the Municipality of Merano, in Meeting Room 104. The event was organised by STA in collaboration with Independent L, the Municipality of Merano and the HDS Traders' Association. It served as a pivotal moment for analysing operational strategies and identifying specific requirements related to the implementation of two pilot services in the field of sustainable mobility.

The workshop was attended by institutional representatives, industry experts and local economic stakeholders, including:

- Katharina Zeller, Deputy Mayor and Councillor for Mobility, Municipality of Merano
- Nerio Zaccaria, Councillor for Finance and Budget, Municipality of Merano
- René Rinner, Member of the Special Mobility Unit, Municipality of Merano
- Martin Verdorfer, Member of the Special Mobility Unit, Municipality of Merano
- Martin Stampfer, Head of the Centre of Competence for Urban Development, Sustainability and Digitalisation at HDS
- Joachim Ellmenreich, Representative of local traders on behalf of HDS and owner of "Tabaccheria Ellmenreich" in Merano
- Peter Wenter, Trader, owner of the clothing store "Wenter" in Merano and member of HDS
- Harald Reiterer, Representative of STA, partner of the SuCoLo project
- Olivia Kieser, Representative of STA, partner of the SuCoLo project
- Valentina Mena, Representative of STA, partner of the SuCoLo project
- Günther Ennermoser, Representative of Independent L, partner of the SuCoLo project

The meeting was structured into two distinct thematic sessions. The first part focused on the analysis of the cargo bike-sharing service, involving representatives from the Municipality of Merano and the HDS Traders' Association. This session was primarily a discussion on the operational aspects of the service, aiming to define its practical implementation.

The second part centred on the B2C delivery service that will be implemented in Merano and took the form of a targeted co-creation workshop designed to gain a deeper understanding of the needs of local traders through direct input from their representatives.

The primary objective of the workshop was to gather the needs and expectations of the various stakeholders, identify the most effective communication strategies, and define a shared operational plan. Participant engagement was designed to encourage constructive dialogue through brainstorming sessions, targeted discussions and summary moments, with the aim of outlining a clear and methodologically clear path for the implementation phase.

Results

In the workshop dedicated to the B2C delivery service, an in-depth discussion was conducted on the needs of local traders and the most suitable operational methods for the local context. Thanks to the participation of shop owner representatives and HDS members, it was possible to thoroughly analyse the specific requirements of the area. This co-creation workshop helped us identify the key points of interest for the merchants who later joined the project (from February 2025), becoming part of a focus group (11 shops by 12.03.25).

The discussion highlighted the importance of offering multiple ordering options to ensure broad accessibility for customers. As a result, it was decided to maintain three ordering methods:

- Direct in-store purchase
- Telephone orders placed with the retailer
- Orders via webshop

The latter option will undergo further analysis within the focus group, scheduled between March and April 2025, to assess the interest of local businesses in integrating digital channels into their sales models.

Figure 25 Visual Summary of the order process

Table 9 Participants' responses regarding order methods

Order method	Response (accepted, rejected or under evaluation and explanation)
Direct in store purchase	Accepted It represents the most straightforward solution for both order logistics and direct payment.
Telephone order	Accepted Allows participation from target groups, such as elderly individuals or customers who have difficulty reaching the store. Not all retailers offer this service, as preparing orders requires time
Order via webshop	Under evaluation To be assessed with the focus group of participating retailers (March-April 2025). Requires technical integration into the webshops of retailers joining the initiative: extra effort

The payment method was discussed and will be subsequently evaluated by the merchants participating in the focus group. The options to consider include advance payment/deposit, deferred bank transfer, and direct payment to the courier, to be used exclusively in exceptional cases. Additionally, the option of a direct bank transfer via systems such as Satispay and PayPal will be suggested as alternative to traditional paying methods.

Table 10 Participants' responses regarding paying methods

Paying method	Response (accepted, rejected or under evaluation and explanation)
In-store Payment	Accepted Considered the standard option for direct in-store purchases
Advance Payment/Deposit	Under evaluation to be assessed based on the merchant., considered suitable for regular customers
Post-payment via Bank Transfer	Under evaluation to be assessed based on the merchant
Direct Payment to Courier	Accepted but applicable only in exceptional cases, as it involves more workload for the courier
Bank Transfer via Satispay/PayPal	Under evaluation to be assessed based on the merchants' experience with these platforms

The delivery costs proposed by FIX Courier by bike have been examined, with different price categories based on the delivery area. The proposed price categories are as follows:

- Zone A: €8.50 applicable to the Merano city centre area
- Zone B: €11.50 for the areas of Lagundo, Marlengo and Sinigo

Lieferung Kosten FIX Courier

Zone A = Meran (Stadtzentrum, Untermais, Obermais)	
Einzelne Lieferung (garantierte Zustellung innerhalb desselben Tages)	8,50 €
Einzelne Lieferung EXPRESS (Zustellung innerhalb 60 min ab Anruf)	12 €
Ab der zweiten Lieferung pro Tag	7,50 € 6,50 € (ab der 5. Lieferung)
Hin- und Rückfahrt	+ 4 €
Zuladung >40 kg	+ 4 €
Zone B = Alquid, Marling, Tschermers, Sinich, Lana Industriezone	Zone A + 3 €
Regelmäßige Lieferungen / Daueraufträge / Außergewöhnliche Transporte	Nach Vereinbarung

Figure 26 Description of delivery costs from Fix Courier

During the planning phase, it was decided to initially exclude Zone B, except for Sinigo, as it is part of the Municipality of Merano. The possibility of extending the delivery service to Zone B will be re-evaluated at a later stage, based on demand and the availability of funding within the allocated budget.

Table 11 Participants' responses regarding delivery zones

Delivery zone	Response (accepted, rejected or under evaluation and explanation)
Deliveries in Zone A (€8.50)	Accepted
Deliveries in Zone B, in Sinigo (€11.50)	Accepted As in the municipality of Merano
Deliveries to other neighbouring municipalities, Zone B (€11.50)	Under evaluation Municipalities outside the project's jurisdiction, to be assessed later

From a resource management perspective, an extensive discussion took place on how to ensure an equitable distribution of deliveries among participating shops. Initially, it was proposed to set a limit of 50 orders per shop, but this option was later discarded. Instead, a "first come, first served" system was approved, which will remain in effect until the co-financing limit of €20,000, as defined in the project budget, is reached. This approach provides greater flexibility for the retailers, better aligning with their operational needs.

Regarding the delivery costs, extensive discussions were held. It was ultimately decided that a fee of €2 will be charged to the retailer and €2 to the customer, while the remaining cost will be covered by STA. This cost-sharing arrangement helps balance the financial burden among the parties involved while maintaining the financial sustainability of the project.

Table 12 Participants' responses to proposed delivery distribution options

Option	Response (accepted, rejected or under evaluation and explanation)
Limit of 50 orders per shop	Rejected
"First arrived, first served" option (up to the €20,000 cap)	Accepted approved to ensure flexibility and fairness in order distribution
Delivery cost: more than €2 charged to the retailer, more than €2 charged to the customer	Rejected considered too burdensome for both parties
Delivery cost: €2 for the retailer + €2 for the customer, with the remainder covered by STA	Accept deemed adequate and sustainable for all parties involved
The delivery will only proceed if the order amount exceeds 10 euros.	Accept to avoid processing small orders that do not justify the effort.

Communication has been identified as a key element for the success of the project. Retailers emphasized the importance of presenting the service as an added value for local commerce, highlighting the opportunity to compete with large online platforms through a system of fast and sustainable deliveries. This approach enables the enhancement of physical stores' offerings, differentiating them from large-scale digital solutions.

It was also agreed that the project should ensure adequate visibility for participating shops through a targeted communication strategy, which includes promotion on social media, local media outlets and integrated supportive communication.

In this regard, local WhatsApp groups have been identified as one of the primary tools for the dissemination and multiplication of information related to the project, to engage a wide and diverse audience.

Planning of future activities

During the discussion, the best strategy for engaging retailers was explored. A proposal was made to schedule an informal meeting in February, coinciding with the reopening of stores after the winter break. According to the representatives, most shops close after the Christmas and winter tourist season. However, this event did not take place, as there was insufficient interest from the merchants. Consequently, the approach shifted to a more direct "call to action", which was launched in March. This led to the enrolment of 11 retailers (as of 12 March 2025), who will now participate in the project's focus group.

Lessons learned & next steps

The workshop highlighted several crucial aspects for the successful implementation of the project. It became clear that the active involvement of retailers is essential for the effective operation of the delivery service, as is the need for clear and targeted communication. Another significant factor is the flexibility of the ordering methods, which must incorporate both digital tools and more traditional approaches to ensure inclusive access for all customers.

In February, a call to action was sent to the retailers, considering all the aspects discussed during the workshop.

To maintain high levels of engagement and gather continuous feedback, regular meetings and workshops will be organized with the retailers and other stakeholders involved. Additionally, success indicators will be defined to monitor the project's impact and implement any necessary improvements. These indicators will be grouped into key categories:

- ✓ Order Metrics: Number of orders, methods used and locations
- ✓ Stakeholder Engagement: Retailer and customer participation, including motivations for joining the initiative

MOVE to CARGO

Fahrradlieferungen mit cargobike: um die Wettbewerbsfähigkeit deines Geschäfts zu steigern, die Kundenfrequenz zu erhöhen und für ein lebenswerteres Meran.

Von Mai 2025 bis Juni 2026

STA – Südtiroler Transportstrukturen AG und hds – Handels- und Dienstleistungsverband Südtirol in Zusammenarbeit mit Fix-Fahrradkurier und der Gemeinde Meran, starten eine Initiative zur Förderung von Fahrradlieferungen zur Unterstützung des lokalen Handels in Meran.

Wie laufen die Lieferungen ab?

Hauslieferungen durch Fix-Fahrradkurier für deine Kunden im Gemeindegebiet von Meran (BZC)

Lieferungen durch Fix-Fahrradkurier an eine neue Pick-up-Box (Ermes s.r.l) am Meraner Presserembahn, speziell für Pendler und Anwohner

→ **Vergünstigte Lieferkosten:** 2 € zu Lasten der Kaufleute, 2 € der Kunden, der Rest wird von STA übernommen

→ **Promotionswochen** mit Lieferkosten, die vollständig von STA übernommen werden

Digitale Plattform zur Verwaltung von Bestellungen und Kommunikation zwischen Geschäft und Kurier

Wer kann den Service nutzen?

→ Der Service gilt nur für Geschäfte im Gemeindegebiet von Meran

Transportierbare Waren: Lebensmittel*, Bücher, Arzneimittel, Kleidung, Blumen, kleine Elektrogeräte, Bastelbedarf und mehr

*Achtung: Der Service ist nicht geeignet für verderbliche Waren (Tiefkühlprodukte, sensible Frischprodukte) sowie für gefährliche Güter oder Waren über 40 kg

Was sind die Vorteile des Service?

→ **Erhöhte Sichtbarkeit** für dein Geschäft durch eine kontinuierliche Informationskampagne (Veranstaltungen, soziale Medien, Flyer, Pressekonferenzen)

→ **Interaktive Workshops** zur Unterstützung und Beratung

→ **Schnelle Lieferungen**, um mit Online-Shops außerhalb der Region zu konkurrieren

Eine Möglichkeit, verantwortungsbewusste Einkäufe zu fördern

Bei Interesse kontaktiere uns bitte bis zum 26.02.25

Haast du weitere Fragen?

Marin Stampfer, hds – Handels- und Dienstleistungsverband Südtirol:
MStampfer@hds-bz.it

Valentina Mena,
STA - Südtiroler Transportstrukturen AG:
movetocargo@sta.bz.it

Dieser Service ist Teil des Forumprojekts SuCoLo, ein nachhaltiges Kooperationsmodell in realen Geschäften und deren Partner fördert und unterstützt Shopping-sustainable consumer behaviour with inclusive bicycle logistics infrastructure in urban outskirts. This project has been funded by the FFG, MMT, EMRF and Innova under the Calling Urban Innovations Partnership which has been co-funded by the European Union. Dieses Projekt wird von der Europäischen Union und dem Netzwerk der EU-Förderer unterstützt.

Figure 27 The call to action was shared in the two WhatsApp groups of retailers in Merano (both HDS members and non-members, with the help of Joachim Ellmenreich)

5. Conclusion

The activities undertaken within T3.2 (and to some extent within T4.1 and T5.3) of the SuCoLo project have led to significant outcomes, demonstrating the effectiveness of open idea challenges and co-creation workshops to engage stakeholders and foster innovative solutions in sustainable last-mile logistics.

The largest activity organised under T3.2 was the international open ideation campaign “Sustainable Last-mile Delivery Heroes” (M9-M13), which engaged the citizens across four partner countries. A total of 53 applications were submitted in four categories (“Behaviour Change”, “Green Online Store”, “Perfect Pick-up Station” and “Ultimate Booking Platform”) with the three best ideas selected. All submitted solutions are available on IdeaSpace platform, and the project consortium has access to them for consideration and potential integration into further project tasks.

The Italian campaign “My Merano, My Cargobike” (M12-13) actively involved local citizens in selecting the best names for the cargo bikes and the electric scooter to be used during the piloting stage. A total of 48 name ideas were submitted, with six winning names chosen: CaptainCargo, CargoLina, C. Argonaut, EcoMover, Pass(r)gino and Sissi-Cruiser.

Both idea challenges involved expert juries (12 experts in total) and the community (more than 2,000 active members of the IdeaSpace platform) in selecting the best solutions. All ideas submitted are available to the project partners on Idea Space and can be taken into account during the pilot phase and in ongoing communication and dissemination activities.

An essential part of the work was organising and facilitating three co-creation workshops in Salzburg (M9, organised by SFRG), Leipzig (M13, organised by the University of Leipzig and the City of Leipzig’s Office of Economic Development) and Merano (M11, organised by STA Independent L, the Municipality of Merano and the HDS Traders’ Association). These sessions gathered a total of 34 stakeholders and provided valuable insights into key issues related to sustainable logistics solutions using cargo bikes and sustainable delivery options. These workshops contributed essential input for the preparation of the SuCoLo research pilots.

During the Salzburg workshop, participants gave detailed feedback on the webshop prototype designed to integrate BCTs for promoting sustainable delivery behaviours. The session also focused on developing a pick-up station concept that considers local and social conditions. Key suggestions included enhancing text and image contrast for better readability, updating the homepage image to display realistic cargo bike-compatible products, modifying the shopping cart to show shipping costs only after a delivery method is selected, etc.

The Leipzig co-creation workshop gathered insights from residents of Lützschena-Stahmeln district, representatives of the City of Leipzig and employees from a local bike courier service. Discussion focused on understanding citizens’ daily mobility and shopping behaviour and on developing a sustainable and inclusive delivery concept that addressed local needs. Workshop outputs informed the development of a survey questionnaire to collect additional detailed information about the residents’ habits. These findings will be incorporated into design of the Leipzig research pilot.

The Merano co-creation workshop served as a pivotal moment for analysing operational strategies and identifying specific requirements for implementing two local pilot services in sustainable mobility. The primary objective was to gather the needs and expectations of

various stakeholders, identify effective communication strategies and define the operational plan. The workshop underlined the needs for active involvement of retailers and the importance of clear targeted communication. It also emphasised the necessity for the flexible ordering methods, combining both digital tools traditional approaches to ensure inclusive access for all customers. It was decided that webshop ordering option would be analysed through a focus group to assess local businesses' interest in integrating digital channels into their sales models.

The idea competitions and local workshops were widely promoted by project partners to engage the audience, which also contributed significantly to the project dissemination. Over 80 social media posts were published, reaching more than 4,000 people on LinkedIn, alongside additional outreach through newsletters, individual emails and other channels. Furthermore, the "Sustainable Last-mile Delivery Heroes" campaign was integrated into different courses at the University of Applied Sciences Salzburg, FHNW University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland and University of Leipzig, as well as promoted during other events (e.g., the mobility workshop in Bolzano, 17.10.24).

The insights and outcomes gained from the ideation campaigns and co-creation workshops form a strong foundation for the successful implementation of the project. The feedback collected offers a clear roadmap for future improvements and provides valuable inputs for the next project tasks, which focus on preparing and implementing the SuCoLo research pilots and project dissemination (T3.3 "Inventory of behaviour change strategies for sustainable consumer logistics choices," T3.4 "Behaviour change guidebook and digital behavioural interventions tool," T4.1 "Design and prepare accessible and inclusive pilots with local stakeholders," T4.2 "Run and evaluate pilots in communities of local neighbourhoods", T4.3 "Adoption plans of follower cities," T4.4 "Toolkit for bicycle hubs & sustainable logistics in urban outskirts", T5.1 "Disseminate project results and products," T5.2 "Support adoption and scaling in follower cities", T5.3 "Events, presentations and publications").

References

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